

A Review on Reducing Complexity of Binary Search Algorithm

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Extended Abstract: Binary search is a widely used search algorithm that has applications in various fields, including computer science, data science, and engineering. It is known for its efficiency, as it has a time complexity of $O(\log n)$, where n is the number of elements in the list. However, the efficiency of binary search heavily depends on the size of the list and the way the list is sorted. Therefore, there is a need for optimization techniques to improve the performance of binary search on larger lists. Binary search optimization refers to the process of modifying the algorithm to reduce its time complexity or improve its performance. The primary goal of binary search optimization is to reduce the number of comparisons required to find the desired element in the list. Various approaches have been proposed to optimize binary search, including interpolation search, exponential search, and fractional cascading. Interpolation search is a modification of binary search that uses an interpolation formula to estimate the position of the search element in the list. This technique is particularly effective when the list is uniformly distributed. Exponential search is another optimization technique that involves starting the search from the first element and doubling the search range until the element is found. Fractional cascading is a method that reduces the number of comparisons by using pointers to skip over parts of the search space that do not contain the search element. Overall, binary search optimization is an essential area of research that aims to improve the efficiency and performance of binary search. By reducing the number of comparisons required, these optimization techniques can significantly reduce the time complexity of the algorithm and make it even more efficient for practical applications.

The primary objective of this review is to provide a concise yet comprehensive overview of the various research papers that have been conducted to reduce the complexity of binary search and enhance its efficiency. Binary search is a search technique that is widely used to search for a particular element in a sorted list. The process entails dividing the list into two halves and comparing the search element with the middle element of the list. If a match is found, the location of the middle element is returned; otherwise, the search continues in either of the halves, depending on the result produced by the comparison. This review includes an analysis of more than ten research papers that have attempted to improve the performance and efficiency of binary search. The articles used in this study were obtained from various sources on the internet. The primary aim of these papers is to reduce the complexity of binary search and make it even more efficient. Specifically, this review focuses on three research articles that meet the prerequisites of this review. Through this review, readers will gain valuable insights into the different approaches used to improve the efficiency of binary search, as well as the advantages and limitations of these approaches. The review will also provide an in-depth analysis of the key findings of the selected research articles, highlighting their contributions to the field of binary search optimization.

The goal of this review is to summarize existing research papers that focus on reducing the complexity of binary search and making it more efficient. We have searched for related research articles using databases such as IEEE, ACM, Google Scholar, Springer, Elsevier, PubMed, and ResearchGate. The search criteria included keywords such as Binary Search, Algorithm Efficiency, Sorting and Searching, Time Complexity, and the articles had to be composed in the English language.

Through our search, we found more than ten research papers on binary search. Three of these papers were reviewed in detail. Kunal et al. [1] proposed a decomposed algorithm to reduce the time complexity of binary search. The traditional binary search algorithm has a time complexity of $O(\log(n))$ where n is the length of a sorted list. However, using the decomposed algorithm, the time complexity can be reduced to $O(\log(k))$, where $k < n$ and k is the length of the sub-list. Ankit et al. [2] proposed an approach to optimize binary search further. They suggested checking the beginning and end points of the list first to see if the desired number is present there. This is because the numbers in the beginning and end positions typically have the worst complexity. By checking these points first, the algorithm can be more optimized. The third article by Ravi et al. presents a hybrid search algorithm that combines binary search with interpolation search. The hybrid algorithm first performs an interpolation search to estimate the target element's position and then uses binary search to find the exact position of the target element. This approach significantly reduces the number of iterations required for the search and can improve the algorithm's performance on large and unstructured data sets. Other research papers on binary search have also explored various ways to reduce its complexity and improve its efficiency. For example, some papers have focused on parallelizing the algorithm to make it run faster on multi-core processors, while others have looked at using machine learning techniques to predict the best search strategy for a given input list. In conclusion, binary search is a widely used searching technique, and there are several ways to reduce its complexity and improve its efficiency. The research papers we reviewed have proposed various approaches such as decomposed algorithms, optimized checking, parallelization, and machine learning to achieve this goal.

Index Terms: Binary Search, Algorithm Efficiency, Sorting and Searching, Time Complexity.

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